

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions

(A Peer Reviewed Journal)

www.ijmrt.in

Improving Quality of Educational Institutes using Online Mode of Learning

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Abstract

The Quality of education can be improved by using various advanced tools in the teaching and learning process. The present age is on Online learning many students are opting for online learning platform . The Educational Institutes world wide should make use of this opportunity and create the various facilities form onlearning platforms. The Basic infrastructure and various software's are required to implement educational activities in the online mode . activities should be planned well in advance before the starting of the academic year . Good quality hardware and software for using the educational apps and also good expert support from back office is required for quality learning and teaching platform. Online education is a flexible instructional delivery system that encompasses any kind of learning that takes place via the Internet. Online learning gives educators an opportunity to reach students who may not be able to enroll in a traditional classroom course and supports students who need to work on their own schedule and at their own pace.

The quantity of distance learning and online degrees in most disciplines is large and increasing rapidly. Schools and institutions that offer online learning are also increasing in number. Students pursuing degrees via the online approach must be selective to ensure that their coursework is done through a respected and credentialed institution.

Keywords: Education, quality, Online , Student, Teacher , Software , Hardware , Server.

Subject classification: Quality in Education , Online Learning

1. Introduction

It is an instructional methodology, a teaching and learning approach that combines face to-face classroom methods with computer mediated activities to deliver instruction. This pedagogical approach means a mixture of face-to-face and online activities and the integration of synchronous and asynchronous learning tools, thus providing an optimal possibility for the arrangement of effective learning processes. Blended learning is the term given to the educational practice of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching. In a true blended learning environment, both the student and the teacher should be physically located in the same space. Despite this, the digital tools used should be able to be utilised by the students in order to enforce some control over the speed or topics of their learning. The flipped classroom model is a similar program that aims to utilise technology in order to rearrange the learning experience and maximise the effectiveness of valuable face to face time in the classroom. Need for Flexibility to Students / Learners Centricity The National Education Policy has given a rare glimpse in what can be achieved through the transformation of education. The new NEP clearly states that it is time to take on a policy that is undoubtedly student centric, or what can be safely put down as Education 4.0! The time has indeed come to recognize the fact that the student is the main stakeholder and that efforts must be taken to make the system respond to their dreams and aspirations.

Source :- <https://www.google.com/search?q=online+education&source>

In this line of thinking the new policy gives the acceptability of many modes of learning including that of face to face learning, online learning and distance or virtual mode. It also promotes use of vocational courses, multi-disciplinary courses and multi-modal approaches there by focussing on quality and defining quality: a complex and multi-dimensional concept

The concept of quality is much disputed in higher education and often used by stakeholders in order to legitimize their specific vision or interests. Two reasons can be given for the difficulties encountered when defining quality in higher education:• There is no consensus on the exact objectives of higher education – although some objectives can be named, such as to produce a qualified work force, to train people for a career in research, to provide efficient management of the teaching profession, and to enhance life prospects.

Definition: A learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of electronic resources is known as online learning. While teaching can be based in or out of the classrooms, the use of computers and the Internet forms the major component of online learning. Also termed as E-learning can also be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, and the delivery of education is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times. Earlier, it was not accepted wholeheartedly as it was assumed that this system lacked the human element required in learning. However, with the rapid progress in technology and the advancement in learning systems, it is now embraced by the masses. The introduction of computers was the basis of this revolution and with the passage of time, as we get hooked to smart phones, tablets, etc, these devices now have an importance place in the classrooms for learning. Books are gradually getting replaced by electronic educational materials like optical discs or pen drives. Knowledge can also be shared via the Internet, which is accessible 24/7.

Online Education -learning has proved to be the best means in the corporate sector, especially when training programs are conducted by MNCs for professionals across the globe

and employees are able to acquire important skills while sitting in a board room, or by having seminars, which are conducted for employees of the same or the different organizations under one roof. The schools which use E-learning technologies are a step ahead of those which still have the traditional approach towards learning. We have to motivate educational Institutes to use online educational platforms for various educational activities and provide quality education to the students.

Source :- <https://www.google.com/search?q=online+education&source=lnms&tb>

2. The Need of Online Learning

The education sector was among the hardest hit by the COVID-19 pandemic. Schools across the globe were forced to shutter their campuses in the spring of 2020 and rapidly shift to online instruction. For many higher education institutions, this meant delivering standard courses and the “traditional” classroom experience through videoconferencing and various connectivity tools. The approach worked to support students through a period of acute crisis but stands in contrast to the offerings of online education pioneers. These institutions use AI and advanced analytics to provide personalized learning and on-demand student support, and to accommodate student preferences for varying digital formats.

Source :- <https://www.google.com/search?q=online+education&source=lnms&tbm>

Colleges and universities can take a cue from the early adopters of online education, those companies and institutions that have been refining their online teaching models for more than a decade, as well as the edtechs that have entered the sector more recently. The latter organizations use educational technology to deliver online education services.

Positive and Negative Effects of Learning Online for the Students

Online education offers many positive benefits since students:

- have flexibility in taking classes and working at their own pace and time
- face no commuting or parking hassles
- learn to become responsible for their own education with information available at their fingertips
- find the submission of assignments easy and convenient
- are more apt to voice their own opinions and share and debate issues with other students, as well as learn from other students during the group discussions

Possible negative effects of learning online are that some students:

- may miss the face-to-face interaction with the instructor and among students
- may prefer to attend traditional classes with an instructor who teaches and guides them through the course

- find access to the necessary technology challenging and the availability of technical support limited

In addition, some administrators and instructors who do not understand the workload may display a negative attitude toward online education.

Role of ICT and its Application in Online Teaching and Learning process

Significant ICT initiatives useful for the higher education teachers of our country while implementing BL are discussed in the following sections. OER: NMEICT, NPTEL, ePG, NDL Open educational resources (OER) are defined by the United Nations as any type of educational materials in the public domain or introduced with an open license. Critical to supporting open knowledge and open access, OER are learning materials supporting legal and free (a) copying, (b) usage, (c) adaptation and (d) sharing. These resources can be anything from textbooks to syllabi, lecture notes, tests, videos or animations. OER offer the opportunity to provide access, quality GUIDE TO BL and cost-effectiveness in education delivery and have led to significant dialogue around policies for knowledge sharing and capacity building in the social and economic global world. While OER are not a necessity for successful BL, these two education innovations combine to make a powerful contribution to high-quality, accessible and affordable education. Using well-designed, available OER can free up resources that can then be used to design and deliver BL opportunities. Creative Commons is a global, collaborative movement for the sharing of free, international, easy-to-use materials. The goal of this international community is to enable greater access and equality; it supports education for everyone. Those who created and now support and use Creative Commons believe in sharing and collaborating on materials such that the full potential of the Web will be realised; most importantly, this will also be true for the individuals who will use it. Creative Commons provides a set of licenses for anyone to use while releasing any teaching or learning resources as OER.

3. Infrastructure and Technolgal Requirements

Technology Infrastructure for Implementation The section discusses the approaches of integrating technology infrastructure and infrastructure requirements. 4.4.1 Approaches likely to be used in BL are as follows: Face-to-face Video Lectures – Shared to the students for the entire course (Pen Drive / CD) - e-textbook experience but not dependent on broadband Internet Based Learning (IBL) – Internet based projects (search & learn) to promote self-learning Project Based Learning – integrating multiple peer group for the project, students to collaboratively generate ideas TAB based remote learning / remote examination & evaluation / touch screens and digital pens appeal to tactile learners / portable learning Satellite based TV proctored examination solutions

4. Future of Online Education

Online teaching is here to stay. Many students prefer the online classroom since it offers flexibility in their busy schedules. With the proliferation of information and knowledge, students must become lifelong learners in today's world, and online education plays an important role in helping individuals access the learner-centered and self-directed instruction.

With enhanced software, hardware, and Internet access, more options for online education will become available. With student enrollments increasing faster than classrooms can be built, students becoming more proficient with technology, and students pursuing an education that meets their needs, the future of online education will continue to grow. Online degree programs will become more widely accepted as they become a more common practice.

Source :- <https://www.google.com/search?q=online+education&source>

5. Conclusion

The quality of education is a complex process and affects the important year of the youth of any country the role of online learning and teaching in this present age is must for the benefit of the educational sector . Online learning has become the need of the hour for the higher educational sector since the students community are now looking for the various advanced modes of learning tools and get the maximum benefits of the education process. The use of new technology for teaching like computer softwares and various new tools is going to be the future of the educational sector in the near future. Students will demand various ways of providing the education to them. This paper is a decent effort in creating the awareness among the stakeholders of the educational sector about this important topic to the society as a whole.

Acknowledgment

The Author is thankful to Management of Bharati Vidyapeeth for motivating in writing this paper for the cause of academics. We are also thankful to authors whose references are used here..

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